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MODELING OF MODULUS EVOLUTION FOR PROCESS SIMULATION

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Tribute to Professor Scott White

- Process simulation was one of Professor Scott White's many key contributions to the field of composites
- An early contributor to the topic of residual stress development during processing, Professor White presented one of the earliest viscoelastic models
- This presentation touches on a conceptually simple but very important issue in process simulation – how to represent the elastic and viscoelastic material constants for the curing resin

Outline

- Importance of Process Simulation to reduce manufacturing risk
- Physics-based Process Simulation
- History of Process Simulation of Composites
- Constitutive Models for Residual Stress prediction
- (E, ν) or (K, G) ?
- Concluding remarks

Introduction

- Composite materials have revolutionized the aerospace and increasingly other industries
- It has taken a long time to mature the underlying science and technology and reduce risk and enable adoption at current scales of size, complexity, and production rate
- A major challenge with composites is that the material is transformed during an essentially in-situ manufacturing process. This increases the importance of understanding what happens to the material during the manufacturing process.
- Process simulation has therefore played a major role in risk reduction and technology adoption

From Coupon to Full-scale Composite Structures

Bilding Block Approach

A Typical Manufacturing Building Block Approach:

QUESTION:
Are we testing the same at all levels:

- Material quality
- Residual stresses
- Dimensions

Manufacturing Risk

Simulation Can Help Manage Manufacturing Risk

- Example: Boeing 787 fuselage cure cycle was designed by Boeing-led team using UBC software (COMPRO), commercially supported by UBC spin-off company (CONVERGENT)
- All 787 barrels are cured with one of two cure recipes
 - 297 for Composite Mandrels
 - 297 Mod for Invar Mandrels

Application of Process Simulation in Tool Compensation

Process simulation has become a well-established tool, used by increasing number of companies, for compensated tool design.

Process Simulation

Tool Compensation

Physics-based Process Simulation

- Physics-based modelling is founded on our understanding of *causality* of events.
- The phenomena of interest are modelled using mathematical representations
- In Process Simulation, a physics-based model needs to include representations of:
 - **Material** being processed: its incoming state, its evolution when subjected to process conditions
 - **Process**: Sequence of events and boundary conditions
 - **Equipment**: Interaction of the equipment with material and its effect on process conditions

History of Composites Process Simulation

Composites Process Simulation at UBC

Different Aspects of Composites Process Simulation

Outcomes

Sources of Residual Stress Development during Manufacturing

- Micro-scale: Mismatch between Thermal Expansion of the Resin and Fiber, and Resin's Cure/Crystallization Shrinkage ->Phase-level residual stresses
- Meso-scale: Mismatch between the layers in the laminate ->Ply-level residual stresses
- Macro-scale: Geometric Features, Constraints, Thermal and Cure Gradients, Volume fraction variation, Interaction between the components in an assembly, Tool-part interaction, Machining, etc.
- In order to predict residual stresses and process-induced deformations, it's key to capture the evolution of properties of the constituents during the process:
 - In particular, capturing the evolution of matrix properties: modulus, CTE, CS, and their coordination during the cure cycle is essential

Thermosetting Matrix Properties Evolution

Pre-Gelation:
Liquid Resin + Fiber Bed
Flow Mechanisms:

- Percolation Flow
- Shear Flow

Post-Gelation, Rubbery:
Viscoelastic Response

- Residual stresses start to accumulate
- Resin behaviour is highly viscoelastic exhibiting stress relaxation

Post-Vitrification, Glassy:
Elastic/Hypoelastic Response

- Majority of residual stresses are accumulated at this stage
- Matrix is at this stage in-service

Sequential vs Integrated Process Models

Sequentially Coupled Approach:

- Separate Flow and Stress simulations
- Volume fractions at the end of flow step, typically mapped into the stress-deformation analysis
- Stresses built during pre-gelation and flow regime typically ignored in the stress-deformation simulation

Sequential vs Integrated Process Models

Integrated Flow-Stress (IFS):

- Modelling Pre-gelation and Post-gelation regimes under the same simulation framework
- Complete coherence achieved between simulation of pre-gelation->gelation->post-gelation phenomena
- Continuity of stresses and state variables achieved
- Ability to predict porosity, wrinkles and other deposition and pre-gelation defects and carry on their effect on residual stress development

Requires a more holistic view to evolution of matrix properties during cure: viscosity, modulus, CTE and CS. Consistency and coordination during the whole cycle is essential.

Residual Stress Development Constitutive Models

	<u>Model</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Application</u>
Lower Characterization and Computational Costs	Elastic	Not considering properties evolution. Typically used for thermoelastic calculations during cool-down	Showing the trend, quantitatively not accurate
	CHILE/PVE	Cure Hardening Instantaneously Linear Elastic (CHILE) Considering instantaneous (or future forecast) properties of resin to calculate residual stresses	<p>Classic Cure Cycles</p>
	VE/TVE	Viscoelastic Models. Thermorheologically Simple or Complex Considering Stress Relaxation, Thermoelastic Effects	<p>Non-classic cure cycles (e.g. on/off tool curing, post curing)</p> <p>Thicker parts, where shear relaxation is dominant</p>

Modelling Resin Modulus Evolution

- Process simulation is based on capturing the evolution of material properties during the process.
- Two material properties are required to describe the modulus of isotropic resin
- Early works in process modelling are based on Young's modulus (E) and Poisson's ratio (ν):
 - Bogetti and Gillespie (1991), Kim and White (1996 ,1997, 1998, 1999), O'Brien and White (2001, 2003)and Eom, Boogh, Michaud, Sunderland and Manson (2001)
- Later publications (specially in viscoelastic framework) have used Bulk and Shear Modulus of the resin as the building blocks.
 - Simon, Mckenna and Sindt (2000), Prasatya, Mckenna and Simon (2001), Zobeiry, Vaziri and Poursartip (2006).

(E, ν) Issues

- Direct characterization of viscoelastic Poisson's ratio is very challenging.
- Poisson's ratio is not a well defined material property in the rubbery regime (nearly incompressible).
- For a material in the rubbery regime, assuming $G_r \sim 1$ MPa, the bulk modulus value is highly sensitive to small changes in ν :

ν	K_r (MPa)
0.3	2.2
0.48	25
0.49	50
0.499	500
0.4999	5000

Examples of Works using (K , G)

- Some authors assumed constant ν for residual stress analysis (Kim and White, 1996, 1997, 1998, 1999, O'Brien and White, 2001, 2003 and Eom, Boogh, Michaud, Sunderland and Manson, 2001)
- Eom et al (2001) assume a constant ν of 0.3. This causes the rubbery bulk moduli values of the same order of magnitude as the rubbery shear modulus (very small), which in turn results in very small values of stress. (They calculate stresses in the order of 0.001 Pa after gelation and their max stress is in the order of 100 Pa)

g. 9. Calculation of internal stress, conversion and void initiation in the epoxy during cure at 170°C.

Using (E , ν) Pair

- Hilton (2003) comments on the paper by O'Brien and White (2001): *"... the artificial introduction of time invariant PRs [Poisson's ratios] as well as their arbitrary values during property characterizations is contrary to fundamental viscoelasticity principles defining separable solutions and additionally it leads to severe errors in relaxation moduli determinations. These errors further propagate into subsequent stress and strain analyses causing misleading stress level and failure/safety condition designs."*
- O'Brien, Sotto and White (2007) reported cure-dependent viscoelastic Poisson's ratio of an epoxy using moiré interferometry.

Using (K , G) Pair

- In infinitesimal deformation of an isotropic elastic material, changes in size and changes in shape are independent. Therefore K and G are fundamental elastic constants of an isotropic material (Tscheogl, 2002)
- Relaxation of residual stresses are accommodated through shear deformation mode (if allowed). Bulk behavior does not exhibit significant stress relaxation.
- Characterization of G using rheometer and torsional DMTA is straight forward.
- There are experimental difficulties in determining K directly.
- Attempts have been made to obtain K indirectly from two other properties; never been successful.
- Quote from Tschoegl (2002): “ *The determination of $K(t)$ from $E(t)$ and $G(t)$ thus resembles the attempt to determine the weight of the captain by weighing the ship with or without him.*”

Using (K, G) pair to achieve Consistency between Pre- and Post-Gelation Simulations

- In the pre-gelation regime, where most process defects are rooted, the resin is a viscous liquid and a Poisson's ratio is not well-defined.
- Deformation mechanisms include percolation flow (resin relative to fibres) and shear flow (resin and fibres together).
- Bulk modulus of the liquid resin is an important contributor to load sharing between fibre-bed and resin, which will affect the flow mechanisms and formation of defects, such as porosity.
- To integrate the analysis of pre-gelation and post-gelation stages (Integrated-Flow-Stress analysis, Niaki et al, 2017, 2018), a (K, G) formulation is preferred.

Using (K, G) pair to achieve Consistency between Pre- and Post-Gelation Simulations

Examples of Works using (K , G)

- Simon, Mckenna and Sindt (2000), characterized shear modulus of a toughened epoxy resin (Hexcel 8551-7).
- They described time, temperature and degree of cure dependence of the shear modulus using a generalized Maxwell model. The relaxation times were considered to shift with temperature and degree of cure.
- Prasatya, Mckenna and Simon (2001), used a similar model to describe the bulk modulus. They reported the values of glassy and rubbery modulus as 3.2 GPa and 0.62 GPa respectively ($K_r/K_g \sim 0.2$).
- Zobeiry et al (2006) developed a differential viscoelastic formulation to predict residual stresses during cure, considering effect of temperature and degree of cure.

Glassy and Rubbery Bulk modulus values reported in the literature

Researcher	Material
McKinney et al (1960, 1963)	Rubber Sulphur vulcanizate, Poly(vinyl acetate)
Deng and Knauss (1997)	Poly(vinyl acetate)
Sane and Knauss (2001)	Poly(vinyl acetate), Poly(methyl methacrylate)
Prasatya, Simon, Mckenna (2001)	Hexel 8551-7
Alcoutlabi, Mckenna, Simon (2002)	BMI/SOC, Poly(methyl methacrylate)
Meng, Bernazzani, O'Connell, McKenna, Simon (2009)	Polystyrene
Grassia, D'Amore, Simon (2010)	Polycarbonate, Polystyrene, Polycyanurate
Guo, Grassia, Simon (2012)	Linear Polystyrene, Star Polystyrene
Buchenau (2012)	Polyisobutylene, Polyvinylacetate, Polyvinylchloride, Polystyrene, Polymethylmethacrylate, Bisphenol-A-polycarbonate
Sadeghinia, Jansen, Ernst (2012)	Epoxy molding compound (unfilled, fully cured), Epoxy molding compound (filled, fully cured)
Tao and Simon (2015)	Nanoparticle-filled polystyrene nanocomposite

Glassy and Rubbery Bulk modulus values reported in the literature

Using (K , G) Pair

- There is not much agreement on K_r/K_g ratio values in the literature.
- Unlike shear modulus that changes orders of magnitude during cure process, the bulk modulus varies only by a factor of 2 or 3 from glassy to rubbery
- Sensitivity of residual stress predictions to K_r/K_g (within a reasonable range)?
- Corner spring-in values of L-shape angles made of a carbon-fibre composite with symmetric lay-up are considered, for two different thicknesses (aspect ratios):
 - Identical cure cycles
 - K_g is kept constant and K_r value is varied
 - Analysis is performed using COMPRO/ABAQUS process simulation platform

Sensitivity of Residual Stresses to K_r/K_g

K_r/K_g	1	1/3	1/5	1/10
Corner spring-in (thinner part)	1.04	1.04	1.03	1.01
Corner spring-in (thicker part)	0.79	0.78	0.77	0.76

Sensitivity of Residual Stresses to K_r / K_g

- Varying K_r / K_g ratio between 0.1 and 1 does not significantly affect the predicted spring-in value (which is a measure of residual stresses during the process).
- On the other hand, having an accurate model for shear modulus (G) is essential, as the strains built up during the process cycle are relieved through the shear mechanism.
- Fortunately, G can be characterized directly using rheometry and torsional DMTA.
- Even though measuring K is not straight forward, K and G are better representation of mechanical behaviour of the material for residual stress analysis.

Concluding Remarks

- K and G offer a better physical representation of the matrix properties evolution during cure
- Shear deformation mechanism is mainly responsible for stress-relaxation phenomena whereas bulk response does not exhibit significant stress relaxation
- Shear modulus can be characterized directly using rheometry and torsional DMTA.
- Employing G, K pair provides consistency between pre- and post-gelation simulations.

